

Learning to become a Capable and Competent Entrepreneur – Empirical Investigation and Perspectives on an Ethical-oriented Entrepreneurship Education

Research-in-Progress Paper

Robert Lepenies, Wendelin Küpers

Entrehubs Project

Karlsruhochschule International University

Abstract

This research-in-progress paper explores pedagogical approaches for educating future entrepreneurs in ethical and responsible innovation, emphasizing the integration of critical sustainability perspectives into entrepreneurship education. It compares how two different approaches – the European framework for entrepreneurship competences (EntreComp) as well as the Future Skills framework may offer avenues for re-thinking how (entrepreneurship) education is done in universities. The paper interrogates these conventional competence-based educational frameworks through a conceptual analysis and proposes a reclassification of such entrepreneurial learning through a capabilities-perspective. A recent online Summer School on entrepreneurship is used to showcase this approach in practice, highlighting various teaching methods, including experiential learning, project-based learning, and inter- & transdisciplinary collaboration in an intercultural setting informed by sustainability sciences.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship Education, Critical Entrepreneurship Studies, Ethical-oriented Education, Future Skills, Experiential Learning, Sustainability Sciences, Intercultural Competence*

Introduction

For some time skills and competencies in and for entrepreneurship have been an established area of teaching and practice (e.g. Hagg and Kurczewska, 2022). Alongside more mainstream approaches to studying entrepreneurship, the field of critical entrepreneurship studies has developed (Nodoushani and Nodoushani, 1999; Tedmanson et al. 2012) to embrace more humanistic and liberal studies, including critical reflection about cultural, social, political and ecological contexts. This reflection sometimes includes rethinking the notion of entrepreneurship as “entrepreneurship”: Seeing competencies but also capabilities required in entrepreneurship are neither fixed traits nor predetermined static ‘units’, but need to be seen dynamically, as developed and learnt through embodied experiences and corresponding training and deliberate practices (van Gelderen, 2023). Entrepreneurship education is situated at the crossroads and called to challenge assumptions that were taken for granted and open up for new perspectives (Loi et al. 2022). There are various competence models and competence-based education available (Lille and Taeks 2017).

The paper explores how entrepreneurship programs can be ‘subversively’ used to cultivate such critical capabilities and competencies (and corresponding methods), especially against selected areas of the European entrepreneurship education frameworks as a folio.

What becomes increasingly important is to develop and reflect a more holistic approach to entrepreneurship education. Such an approach needs to encompass not only business-specific knowledge, but also personal development, social and ethical dimensions, as well as adaptability to technological advancements and socio-cultural developments. This broader and more integral perspective on value creation is important as more impactful ventures will become vital. In particular, ethical (dispositions/capabilities) and sustainability- and responsibility-oriented thinking, together with being able to deal with uncertainty and ambiguity are important. We propose that in a complementing relationship with other competencies these help (future) entrepreneurs identify opportunities to create value not just for themselves, but for the increasingly endangered environment and a changing society as well.

First a conceptual base is distinguishing capabilities, and competencies, then secondly selected competencies of the European competence framework EntreComp and the so-called Future Skills frames are analysed and discussed critically. This new approach to rethinking entrepreneurship education is currently developed as a standalone course. A module for Bachelor students is currently being developed that should encapsulate this capability-oriented focus on critical entrepreneurship. A first experimental, transnational summer school financed by the European Union is currently underway (July 2024) in which aspects of this course are being tested.

The paper will include an empirical analysis of this experimental summer school through a survey that was fielded to this transnational group of students enrolled in the entrepreneurship summer academy. The survey includes both closed-ended questions to quantify ambiguity tolerance (Dalbert, 2019) and ethical competence alongside the competence frameworks, and furthermore includes open-ended questions to explore students' reflections on their learning experiences, ethical challenges faced, the notion of entrepreneurship in times of existential sustainability challenges and the development of intercultural competencies.

Conceptual Foundation on Capability & Competency

The terms competence, capability and capacity are often used interchangeably. Furthermore, the literature on professional capacities is full of non-specific operationalizations (Ambrosini and Bowman, 2001; Davis, 2011). Considering (adult & systems) developmental perspective and knowledge, the following section offers some clarifications and distinctions and argues that both and a specific integrative relationship between them are necessary for accomplishing the goal of ‘Bildung’ as transformative education here in relation to entrepreneurship. Accordingly, students of entrepreneurship should be competent and capable for performing in effective, transformational (double & triple loop change) and sustainable ways. Both competencies and capabilities refer to learnable capacities that are supportive and facilitate transformation in contexts of complexity, uncertainty, unknowing, and ambiguity while being able to sense and make sense (meaning making maturity) of systemic and socio-ecological challenges, patterns and meta-patterns.

Conceptual Foundation on Capability & Competency

The terms competence, capability and capacity are often used interchangeably. Furthermore, the literature on professional capacities is full of non-specific operationalizations (Ambrosini and Bowman, 2001; Davis, 2011). Considering (adult & systems) developmental perspective and knowledge, the following section offers some clarifications and distinctions and argues that both and a specific integrative relationship between them are necessary for accomplishing the goal of 'Bildung' as transformative education here in relation to entrepreneurship. Accordingly, students of entrepreneurship should be competent and capable for performing in effective, transformational (double & triple loop change) and sustainable ways. Both competencies and capabilities refer to learnable capacities that are supportive and facilitate transformation in contexts of complexity, uncertainty, unknowing, and ambiguity while being able to sense and make sense (meaning making maturity) of systemic and socio-ecological challenges, patterns and meta-patterns.

Competency

A competency is the quality or state of being functionally adequate or having sufficient information, knowledge, 'strength', and skill. An individual's skill refers to the acquired ability to use his or her knowledge effectively and readily in execution or performance.

For some longer time there exist a differentiated discourse and critique related to competency-based education and a debate about its a way of framing education and training (Edwards, 2016). Especially behaviouristic performance-assessing conceptions of competencies have been seen as being part of a rational-positivistic paradigm, that is being imposed hierarchical, and deterring emancipation or independent and free thought (Brown, 1994). From a critical perspective reductionist competency-based education is interpreted as embedded within a particular set of existing economic, social, and political power relationships that are anti-emancipatory and exploitative, representing and reproducing a neoliberal model of education that adopts and utilizes narrow, functional approaches to education. Extending the reductionist understanding, research informed by phenomenology, has identified different stages of skills acquisition, ranging from novice, advanced beginner, 'competent', proficient, and expert added by mastery and practical wisdom (Dreyfus & Dreyfus 2005).

Capability

Related to its etymological origin and as a more open approach to the '*ability to do*', capability refers to *having the potential to become competent*, as such it is a feature, faculty, or process (of how then applied competencies) that can be developed, deployed, or improved. Furthermore, someone capable is being able *to know what level of competence is needed and to exercise it* (Stephenson, 1998). Moreover, capability includes being aware of the limits of competence as well as potentially how to overcome them in any given situation.

Capable people take an enquiring approach and work their way around problems, rather than accept practices and assumptions as given. They develop new skills and abilities in response to new demands or to improve practice, rather than waiting to be prompted and trained. Importantly they make sound judgements in the face of incomplete information and divergent problems (Schumacher, 1977). Implying being able to become (more) able, a *responsive capability* refers not only to a capacity to develop additional competence, but also to *move beyond competence* to being able to work effectively in unpredictable and changing contexts. As such it requires the *integration of skills, knowledge, ethics and judgment*, including in dealing with unfamiliar problems in unfamiliar contexts (Stephenson, 1998). Being a 'capable practitioner' (O'Reilly et al, 1999) include the ability to go beyond what would normally be considered competent into excellence, creativity or wisdom and to be able to exercise constructively skeptical judgment about the 'right' or 'best' ways of doing things.

While *competence* is typically concerned with fitness *for* purpose or getting the job right, *capability* infers concern also with *fitness of purpose* or making judgments about the right job to do (Lester and Chapman, 2000: 2). Capability suggests a *conceptually higher level of operation* than that typically captured in most notions of competence. A capability approach is able to *inform and modify competence frameworks* so that they represent something that better reflects professional work, taking account of things that characterize the working environments of many professions such as emergent contexts, evolving and contested practices and the need for intelligent judgement and lived ethical practice (Lester 2014).

Capable people are those who know *how to learn*; are creative; have a high degree of self-efficacy; can apply competencies in novel as well as familiar situations; and work well with others. In comparison to competency, which involves a more specific acquisition of knowledge and skills, capability is a more holistic attribute and performative practice. Organizational learning capabilities are those processes, characteristics or structures which enhance sharing, acquisition and adequate utilization of knowledge within or outside the organization (Cheva, Alegra & Lapiedra, 2007). In context of organisation research explored the relevance of so-called 'Dynamic Capabilities'. In contrast to *technē* as instrumental skill that is part of professional craft, a *disposition* is a quality of character, a state of readiness, or a potentiality and tendency to act in a specified way that may be learned by habituation, aiming at flourishing or *eudaimonia*, while being oriented towards common good. Being disposed dynamically towards transformative practicing implies a specific (ethical) form(ation) of being and becoming or 'be(com)ing'.

What would it mean to develop a relational understanding of learning, teaching and employing competencies und capabilities related to entrepreneurship as part of interdependent agencies of individual actors and collective agents reinterpreted and reclaimed as embodied practice and part of 'ethi-aesthetics' of existence of the virtuous (in sense of enacting virtuosity) art of life, artful living?

This is precisely what we attempted to do in an experimental summer school that is currently underway. For the paper, we will summarize the learnings from the summer school. Empirically, we both test the impact of the summer school on established competence frameworks but then transcend this empirical discussion with a critical conceptual interrogation

Competence-orientation of existing frameworks

The EntreComp framework, developed by the European Commission, is a detailed model designed to encapsulate and promote entrepreneurship as a crucial skill for lifelong learning. It defines entrepreneurship as the ability to turn opportunities and ideas into value that may be financial, cultural, or social. Organized around three core competence areas—Ideas & Opportunities, Resources, and Into Action—it outlines 15 competences and details eight levels of proficiency, from beginner to expert. This framework is noted for its flexibility, allowing adaptation to different contexts such as education, training, and employment, and aims to foster a common understanding of entrepreneurial competence to enhance personal and professional development in various sectors.

Ethical competence

The EntreComp framework acknowledges ethical and sustainable thinking as a crucial entrepreneurial competency; similarly, the competence is highlighted in the future skills agenda. In the paper, we highlight internal contradictions and shortcomings while proposing an alternative approach to develop ethical entrepreneurial capabilities. These challenges include the complexity of ethical decision-making, the predominance of short-term business focus over long-term ethical considerations, and the lack of structured approaches to nurture these competencies. Additionally, conflicts between ethical practices and other entrepreneurial competencies complicate their integration into everyday business operations. There is a significant need for more structured experiential educational methods, real-world case studies, and enhanced training to better equip entrepreneurs with the necessary tools for ethical and sustainable decision-making.

Dealing with Uncertain & Ambiguity

The EntreComp framework incorporates "ambiguity competence" as a vital skill for navigating today's volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) societal and business environments; similarly, it appears in the Future Skills framework. However, the framework faces several challenges in coherently dealing with uncertainty and ambiguity. These include conceptual problems with the complexity and context-dependent nature of assessing these competencies, the rapid pace of change in business that may outstrip the framework, the subjective nature of evaluations, and the limited focus on the real-world nuances of uncertainty. Additionally, the framework struggles with balancing risk and opportunity, cultural variances, and translating theoretical concepts into practical, actionable strategies.

Interculturality

We similarly note that competence frameworks have hitherto not sufficiently covered competencies and capabilities related to interculturality, which is paramount for entrepreneurship education and practice in

our globalised world. Being able to deal with people from diverse cultures and working internationally (with cultural intelligence) will be paramount for entrepreneurial processes and practices in our globalized world. Entrepreneurship education programs should aim to develop especially the discussed capabilities and competencies to prepare students for the complex and evolving business landscape of the near future. In future papers various theoretical, practical, and political (policy-related) implications and research avenues will be discussed and further perspectives on an integral approach provided.

Conclusion

This 'research-in-progress paper' described an emerging work by laying a conceptual base for distinguishing capabilities, and competencies, critically related to selected capabilities, competencies and skills related to the European competence framework EntreComp and Future Skills framework. The complete paper will outline in more detail educational practices with capability-oriented focus on critical entrepreneurship and findings of an empirical investigation on competencies and experiences of transnational group of students enrolled at an entrepreneurship summer academy with a focus on ambiguity tolerance and ethical competence alongside the competence frameworks. Furthermore, limitations, but also theoretical and practical implications and perspectives will be discussed.

References

- Ambrosini, V. and Bowman, C. (2001). Tacit knowledge: some suggestions for operationalization", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 38 No. 6, pp. 811-829.
- Berglund, Karin & Verduyn, Karen (2018). *Revitalizing entrepreneurship education. Adopting a critical approach in the classroom*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Braun, E., Woodley, A., Richardson, J.T. and Leidner, B., 2012. Self-rated competences questionnaires from a design perspective. *Educational Research Review*, 7(1), pp.1-18. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1747938X11000510>
- Brown, R.B. (1994). Reframing the competency debate: management knowledge and meta-competence in graduate education. *Management Learning*, Vol. 25, No 2, p. 289-99.
- Dalbert, C. (2002). UGTS. Ungewissheitstoleranzskala [Verfahrensdokumentation, Autorenbeschreibung, Fragebogen Deutsch und Fragebogen Englisch]. In Leibniz-Institut für Psychologie (ZPID) (Hrsg.), Open Test Archive. Trier: ZPID. <https://doi.org/10.23668/psycharchives.6592>
- Davis, M. (1999), "Professional responsibility: just following the rules?", *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 65-87.
- Dreyfus, S. & Dreyfus, H. (1980). [A Five-Stage Model of the Mental Activities Involved in Directed Skill Acquisition](#). Washington, DC: Storming Media.
- Edwards, R. (2016). Competence-based education and the limitations of critique *International Journal Training Research*, 14 (3), pp. 244-255.
- Ehlers, U. D. (2022). Future Skills im Vergleich. Zur Konstruktion eines allgemeinen Rahmenmodells für Zukunftskompetenzen in der akademischen Bildung. (englische Übersetzung). https://nextskills.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2022-06-15-Future-Skills-Bildungsforschung_final_Vs_2ENG.pdf
- Ehlers, UD. (2024). Towards a Future Skills Framework for Higher Education. In: Ehlers, UD., Eigbrecht, L. (eds) *Creating the University of the Future. Zukunft der Hochschulbildung - Future Higher Education*. Springer VS, Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-42948-5_2
- Hagg, G. and Kurczewska, A. (2022), *Entrepreneurship Education: Scholarly Progress and Future Challenges*, Routledge, New York.
- Lester, S. (2014). Professional standards, competence and capability, *Higher Education, Skills and Work-based Learning*, Vol. 4 Iss: 1, 31- 43 <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/full/10.1108/HESWBL-04-2013-0005>

- Lester, S. & Chapman, J. (2000). [Beyond conventional competence: a study of capable people](#). Capability "Professional bodies, CPD and informal learning: the case of conservation," *Continuing Professional Development* 2 (4), 110-121.
- Lillevali, U. and T € aks, M. (2017), € "Competence models as a tool for conceptualizing the systematic process of entrepreneurship competence development", *Education Research International*, pp. 1-16, 5160863.
- Loi, M., Fayolle, A., Van Gelderen, M.W., Riot, E. et al. (2022). [Entrepreneurship education at the crossroads: Challenging taken-for-granted assumptions and opening new perspectives](#). *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 31(2), 123-134.
- Nodoushani, O., & Nodoushani, P. A. (1999). A deconstructionist theory of entrepreneurship: A note. *American Business Review*, 17(1), 45.
- O'Reilly D, Cunningham L & Lester S (eds). *Developing the capable practitioner* London, Kogan Page
- Pennetta, Selene, Anglani, Francesco, and Mathews, Shane (2024). [Navigating through entrepreneurial skills, competencies and capabilities: a systematic literature review and the development of the entrepreneurial ability model](#). *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 16(4), pp. 1144-1182. As Pennett et al. (2024) proposes what is needed is an evolving entrepreneurial ability model which interconnects genetic and acquired skill types, capabilities and competencies while being equipped with an Entrepreneurial Skills Map .
- Resch, B., Hoyer, P., & Steyaert, C. (2018). Between critique and affirmation: An interventionist approach to entrepreneurship education. In *Revitalizing Entrepreneurship Education: Adopting a Critical Approach in the Classroom* (pp. 178-196). Taylor and Francis.
- Stephenson, J (1998). The concept of capability and its importance in higher education" in J Stephenson & M Yorke (eds) *Capability and Quality in Higher Education* London, Kogan
- Tedmanson, D., Verduyn, K., Essers, C., & Gartner, W. B. (2012). Critical perspectives in entrepreneurship research. *Organizationn*, 19(5), 531-541.
- Van Gelderen, M.W. (2023). [Developing entrepreneurial competencies through deliberate practice](#). *Education + Training* 65(4), 530-547.
- Verduijn, K., & Berglund, K. (2020). Pedagogical invention in entrepreneurship education: Adopting a critical approach in the classroom. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(5), 973-988. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJEER-04-2018-0274/full/html>
- Vesala-Varttala, T., Humala, I., Isacsson, A., Salonen, A. O., & Nyberg, C. (2021). Fostering Sustainability Competencies and Ethical Thinking in Higher Education: Case Sustainable Chocolate. *eSignals Research*, 2(4). <http://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2021120759474>
- Walmsley, A., & Wraae, B. (2022). Entrepreneurship education but not as we know it: Reflections on the relationship between Critical Pedagogy and Entrepreneurship Education. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(3), 100726.